

Manufacturing process of 100% vegetable composite plates: Effect of the flax-tow grading on mechanical and physical properties

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SUMMARY

Nowadays, the request to use materials preserving the environment is in strong growth. The good mechanical properties and low density of flax fiber allow them to be used as reinforcement in polymeric matrix composite. This research consists in making 100 % vegetable composite plates from flax-tow, thanks to autolinking process developed and protected by ImaP/LTI [6], associated with a thermocompression operation and to compare mechanical and hydral properties of composite plates with different flax-tow grades to make an optimal choice.

Keywords: Biodegradable material, composite, thermocompression manufacturing process, flax-tow.

INTRODUCTION

Natural fibers are divided into three groups: vegetable fibres, animal fibers and mineral fibers. This work will be realised on vegetable fibers and especially on flax fibers.

Vegetable fiber is similar to a composite material reinforced by cellulose fibrils. The matrix is mainly composed of hemicellulose and lignin. Natural fibers being eco-friendly, lightweight, strong, have already start to replace glass and mineral fillers in numerous engineering applications in automobiles, furniture, packaging, and construction [1].

The flax fibers are composed of different fractions: long fibers (20%), short fibers i.e crude flax-tow (15%), shaves (45%) and others (seed and dust). The flax fibers which are generally used for insulation are not exploitable in the textile industry. From flax fibers, many isolating material formats can be produced like wool linen and felt [6]. However, wool linen has good thermal performances but it has not remarkable mechanical properties while felt insulation protects better than the wool linen one against noise, because of its higher density.

The flax fibers can be embedded in polymeric matrices (polypropylene, polyethylene...) to reinforce and achieve desired properties such as impact strength, stiffness, low density, sound damping, and texture together with eco-friendly characteristics in the composites. They were used for reinforcing biopolymers matrix, for example composed of cellulose derivatives, starch, polylactic acid, polycaprolactone... [2, 3, 4, 5]. The hydrophilic nature of fibers is the lack of compatibility with the matrix more hydrophobic. This "incompatibility" results in fibers poor dispersion in the matrix and the formation of a heterogeneous material. Other limitations to the use of natural fibers to reinforce composites are the ability of these composites to retain water and their low thermal stability. These natural fibers begin to deteriorate at 200 °C [10]. Therefore, Bio-composites must be manufactured at the possible lowest temperatures, which limit their applications with some technical polymers.

Traditional biocomposites are made from the combination of different natural fibers with different polymers. The primary functions of resin are to transfer stress between the reinforcing fibers, act as a glue to hold the fibers together, and protect the fibers from mechanical and environmental damage. Resins are divided into two major groups known as thermosets and thermoplastics. In the biocomposite fabrication, each manufacturing technology has its own possibilities and restrictions, and the cost of fabrication part of a composite material generally represents a very competitive challenge. Biocomposites have been traditionally manufactured with techniques like extrusion, injection molding, compression molding, resin transfer molding and pultrusion. Newest researches are made to fabricate 100% vegetable composites based on flax –tow by using the LIN-K process [6].

The pressure method is very popular in the manufacturing of natural-fibre composites because of its high reproductibility and its low cycle time. Thermocompression process combines the action of heat and pressure. For example, the timber industry is already using the thermocompression in composite wood-based.

For environmental and economic goals, STRAMIT [12] was able to produce fully recyclable panels from straw by thermocompression without using resins for walls and floors.

It was shown that some biocomposites materials have interesting specific mechanical properties (Young modulus/density) comparable to composite materials / glass [7].

This work consists in making 100 % vegetable composite plates from flax-tow, thanks to autolinking process developed and protected by ImaP/LTI [6], associated with a thermocompression operation and to compare mechanical and hydral properties of composite plates with different flax-tow grades to make an optimal choice.

MATERIALS AND PROCESSES

Materials

The flax–tow were supplied by CALIRA (Coopérative Agricole Linière de la Region d'Abbeville, France). The crude flax tow used is not cleaned up and contains a shave rate of 50% by mass.

The basic unit of the flax fibre microstructure is composed of cellulose polymer chains aligned and interconnected by microfibrils. They are linked together by lignin, the hemicelluloses and pectins. The amount of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin,

polysaccharides (pectin) and others are cited in table 1 [9]. Mechanical properties of flax fiber are also cited in table 2. [10, 11]

Table 1: flax fiber and flax-shaves composition [9]

	polysaccharides	lignin	cellulose	hémicellulose
Flax fiber	15%	5%	67%	13%
Flax-shaves	10%	24%	53%	13%

Table 2: mechanical properties of flax fibers [10, 11]

	E (GPa)	σ (traction) (MPa)	Density	A (%)
Flax fiber	12-85	600-2000	1,54	1-4

Manufacturing processes of 100% vegetable plates based on flax-tow

In order to have 100% vegetable thin plates and more rigid than the traditional felts, a manufacturing process by thermocompression of agricultural-products has been implemented in this work.

The innovation in the vegetable plates elaborated in this work is that there is no additional resin to bind the flax fibers and it is an organic gel extracted from flax-tow during the manufacturing process that allows this link. Two processes are used in this work: non-oven process and oven-process (fig.1). In fact, in the non-oven-process, flax-tow fibers, blended with water, are directly thermopressed. In the oven-process, flax-tow, blended with water, are submitted to a microwave process, then moulding and drying in an oven [6], then wetted before being thermopressed. The organic binder allowing the linking between the flax-tow is an organic gel extracted during the microwave treatment [6] and the thermocompression of the wet blend [12, 13]. The advantage of the oven and the drying stage is to prevent the creep of the extracted gel.

Figure-1: Oven and non-oven thermocompression processes

All plates used for tests are thermopressed under 200°C. The pressure allows reducing the thickness to 0.2 of its initial thickness.

TEST METHODS

Water absorption

Composite materials were dried at 50°C during 24 hours before water absorption experiments.

Water absorption was determined on plate specimens (40*40*4mm). Samples were measured, weighed and immersed in distilled water maintained at 37°C. The specimens were removed from the storage water at regular intervals, blotted dry and re-weighed till the saturation time is reached. Then, the gain of mass is calculated.

Because there is a lot of shaves linked to flax-tow, the absorption of shaves was determined. A measured mass was immersed in distilled water for 3 hours and then the gain of mass is calculated.

Scanning electronic microscopy

The microstructure morphology and the adhesion between matrix and fibres of various samples were studied by means of scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The micrographs were performed using a PHILIPS FEG XL 30 microscope.

MECHANICAL TESTS

Tensile test

The aim of these tests is to identify the elastic and failure properties and highlight the different stages of their uni-axial tensile behaviour of flax-tow plates. The dimensions of the used specimens are shown in (fig.2). Each specimen is instrumented by an extensometer. The most important difficulty of the tensile tests on vegetable plates resides in the destruction or bending of the specimen under the extensometer weight effect. The use of strain gauges is not possible because of the risk of a local rigidification that distorts the deformation's measurement. Furthermore, it is difficult to stick the gauges because the plates are very porous. All the specimens were dried at 50°C at least 24 h before testing. The tests were conducted under 1 mm/min crosshead speed using a load cell of 5000 N.

Figure 2: tensile test specimen

Charpy impact

Charpy impact strength tests of unnotched specimens were carried out according to standard ISO 179-1 using Advanced Pendulum Impact Tester TINIUS OLSEN- IT503 - type testing machine. Ten samples were tested from each compound and the average results were recorded. All the specimens were conditioned at 23°C at 50%RH at least 24 h before testing. This test was measured in the plates with grinding (1, 2, 4 and 10mm).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phase morphology of Oven-process flax-tow plates

A scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis of the samples shows that an organic gel was extracted during the thermal treatments. This gel allows the linking between the fibers of the flax-tow plate (fig. 3). But, the plate surface was not entirely covered by the gel. SEM analysis with a high magnification shows that the distribution of the gel on the surface of fibers or shaves is not totally uniform probably because the vegetable components have not a complete smooth surface (fig. 3).

Figure 3: Microstructure of 2mm flax-tow plates (Oven process): magnification = 100 (left) and magnification = 2000 (right).

It could be noted that the honeycomb structure of flax shaves which are present too in flax tow based plates has been kept after the pressure application (fig.4). The organic gel does not penetrate into the shaves structure. Consequently this type of plates will be able to present insulating properties.

Figure 4: Scanning electron microscopy analysis of the flax-shaves capillary structure after thermocompression (magnification = 1000)

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Influence of the grade of the flax-tow and the manufacturing process on tensile properties

Preliminary tensile tests (Table 3) lead to the determination of the elastic and failure properties and bulk density which are obtained for different non-oven plates with different grades of flax-tow (1,2,4 and 10mm). Bulk density increases with the decrease of the grade of grinding. It is noted that the mechanical properties in traction are inversely proportional to the size of the flax-tow. For example, the use of grade 10mm instead of 1mm leads to a drop in the material's stiffness of 200 MPa and a decrease of the failure stress by 0.4 MPa. This phenomenon is due to the fact that more the grinding is fine; more there is an extraction of the organic gel, more the composite materials are compact and dense.

The elastic and failure properties of 10mm flax-tow plates made by the oven-process reveals an improvement of mechanical properties of these plates compared to others made by non-oven process. The advantages of the oven-process that there is more of polysaccharides extracted during the microwave treatment. Moreover, the drying in the oven of the mat before thermocompression helps to prevent creep of the extracted gel that improves the mechanical performances of the plates.

Table 3: Mechanical properties of vegetable plates with different flax-tow grades

Specimen	E (MPa)	σ_r (MPa)	ρ (Kg/m ³)
1mm (non-oven process)	300 ± 80	0.7 ± 0.15	810±5
2mm (non-oven process)	200 ± 53	0.65 ± 0.06	760±20
4mm (non-oven process)	140 ± 36	0.6 ± 0.02	720±15
10mm (non-oven process)	100 ± 40	0.3 ± 0.1	695±7
10mm (oven-process)	1171 ± 323	0.63 ± 0.24	780±30

Influence of the grade of the flax-tow to the resistance of Oven- process plates to shock charpy

According to [14], the resistance of flax fibers reinforced polyester matrix to charpy impact increases with the length of fiber. THOMASON [15] found that fiber diameter has a significant effect on composite unnotched impact.

The results of unnotched impact strength of oven-process plates with different grades are presented in the histogram-1. This histogram shows that the impact strength increases with the increase of the grinding grade in opposite order of tensile strength. This is due to the fact that more the fiber is long more the fibre is resistable to impact.

Histogram-1: Flax-tow grade on unnotched charpy impact strength of vegetable plates (Oven- process)

HYDRAL PROPERTIES OF OVEN-PROCESS PLATES

The microwave process of pre-wetted vegetable fibre led to the extraction of water with some polysaccharides such as pectin and hemicellulose. After drying, the presence of these pectins leads to gel the mixture of water and polysaccharides. It has also to be noted the effect of pressure and heat on the depolymerization of polymers and the

esterification of certain substances such as polyphenols (lignin). The new substances which appear should reduce the hydrophilic character of these fibers comparing to the starting substances used. This phenomenon was also verified during the absorption tests. The results of absorption tests give an absorption rate of 718 ± 32 % for the 2mm crude flax-tow and 370 ± 30 for flax-shaves in bulk. However, for plates based on 2mm flax-tow we found a rate of 210% which verifies the hypothesis.

Moreover, many tests of water absorption were realized on plates based on flax-tow (2 and 10 mm) which showed that plates with 10 mm grade absorb at the beginning two and a half times more water than the plates with 1mm. This phenomenon is related to the strong porosity of vegetable composite corresponding to the highest grinding, which allows water to enter the pores easily. However, the time of saturation is almost the same in order of 7 days. The passage of flax-tow from grade 2 to 10mm increases the absorption rate at saturation of 20%.

The kinetics of water absorption of oven-process plates based on 2mm and 10 mm flax-tow over time are presented in (fig.4).

Figure 4: Water absorption of plates (Oven-process) based on 2mm and 10mm flax-tow

CONCLUSION

Two manufacturing processes by thermocompression of lignocellulosic co-products have been implemented in this work in order to have 100% vegetable plates. The influence of the grade of flax-tow on mechanical and hydral plate's properties is studied. The decrease of the grade of flax-tow grinding improves the interfacial interaction between fibres because more we have thin grinding more we extract organic gel that can improve mechanical properties in traction. The plates made by oven process have mechanical properties better than others made by non-oven process.

The increase of the grade of the flax-two grinding increases the impact strength of the oven process plates because more the fiber is long more it is resistant to impact.

Moreover, the decrease in grinding flax-tow leads to a more compact material which reduces the hydrophilic character of this type of vegetable composites.

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